

MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Annotation: This article discusses the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in foreign language teaching methods and their use.

Keywords: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competencies, didactics, intercultural communication.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается о методике обучения иностранному языку, истории его развития как науки, видах современных методов, применяемых в методике обучения иностранному языку и их использовании.

Ключевые слова: методика, инновация, иностранный язык, коммуникация, навыки, компетенция, дидактика, межкультурная коммуникация.

Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of

innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. It is an innovation process studied the classification of participants, their attitude to the news, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas. "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that affected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, our President named this year as "Year of Youth Support and Public Health", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be wrong to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the fields of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology.

Learning and teaching foreign languages in many ways involves the issues of foreign language teaching methodology from a theoretical point of view. depends on the development and creative application of the theory in practice.

The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of education through the subject of a foreign language, the science of teaching a foreign language, the study of teacher and student activity is considered the subject of the methodology. The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? is the content of teaching. Methodology - how do we teach? means educational methods and methods. The concept of method - methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and

means ways leading to a certain goal, a method. In various literature, you can find the narrow and broad meaning of the term. "Methodology The term " in a narrow sense refers to the concept of education related to the concrete lesson process. It is interpreted as a controlled lesson process that includes instructions related to the planning of lessons and the preparation of educational materials. "Method The term "in a broad sense refers to the selection, classification and distribution of educational material. In the Federal Republic of Germany, since the 1960s, "didactics" and "methodology" have been used in a narrow sense. Accordingly, the content of didactic education What is taught? Methodology deals with the issues of how educational methods are taught. Learning foreign languages is not only a means of intellectual education, but also an opportunity to get acquainted with the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and learn them. z from It is the process of forming a person's personality by applying it to his life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools are seen as educating the privileged few. The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methodology were expressed. One of these views belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba. In his opinion, although the methodology of teaching any subject is a subject, it is not considered a theoretical subject. It solves practical issues. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on psychological evidence, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these

laws. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phonetists and a great English linguist, O. Yesperson, who is considered the most original phonetist and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, the 19th century among the most prominent French linguists at the end and beginning of the 20th century are F. Bruns and Bréal, a prominent Anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyodor, and others. Academician L.V. Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist scientist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists have a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching. Professor V.A. Artemov made a valuable comment about the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how the teacher conducts the lesson. Psychology deals with how students learn this subject. However, this opinion cannot be fully agreed.

Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology. A deeper study of the literature on the history of methodology shows that some researchers call methodology an art. They usually refer to the idea of the French Methodist Penlache, that there are no "good" or "bad" methods, there are "good" or "bad" teachers. People who have such an opinion can be answered with the thoughts of the German Methodist E. Otto, expressed in 1924. He says: "If someone considers methodology to be an art, he confuses the theory of science with its practical application." Each discipline has its own set of concepts. Among the main concepts adopted in the foreign language teaching methodology, the following can be

included: educational system, educational method, educational principle, educational tool, methodical method.

Foreign language teaching method means a set of teacher and student activities that ensure achievement of practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals of foreign language teaching. The term method is used in the sense of "set of educational methods" and "direction of education". First, in the theory of education, the process is used in the sense of methods, and in the second sense, we can find it in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, the translation method, the correct method, the conscious-comparative method, the traditional method, the intensive method, etc.

Expressing grammatical knowledge is considered to be the main goal of education. The main principles of this method are as follows:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, and the lexicon was chosen accordingly. Grammar exercises were the main method of work.
3. First, grammatical rules were memorized, and then it was recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. Grammatical forms and the meaning of words are revealed through literal translation.
5. Language material is mastered by literal translation and dry memorization.
6. Limited to individual memorization of words out of context.

Method without translation. Various forms of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two large groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to the conditions of acquiring the mother tongue. The main goal of the method is to create an opportunity to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language. The most important of the principles included in the natural method is to create a language environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of the advanced methodical principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents.

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